

PSYCHODIAGNOSTIC FEATURES OF PLAY THERAPY IN CHILDREN OF SMALL SCHOOL AGE.

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Annotaytsiya: Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolani shaxs sifatida shakillanishi. Rivojlanishning ma'lum bosqichi sifatidagi ahamiyati. Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar emotsional sohasining o'ziga hosliklari. Ta'lim jarayonida emotsional barqarorlikning(o'yin terapiyasi) ahamiyati.

Kalit so'zlar: Emotsiya, emotsional barqarorlik, ta'lim samaradorligi,

Annatatsion: The formation of a child's a person of junior school age. Importance as a certain stage of development. Peculiarities of the emotional sphere of children of primary school age. The importance of emotional stability in the educational process.

Key word: emotion, emotional stability, educational efficiency.

Аннотация: Личность маленького ребенка школьного возраста шаткая как личность. Важность на определенной стадии развития. Особенности эмоциональной сферы детей младшего школьного возраста. Значение эмоциональной устойчивости в образовательном процессе.

Ключевые слова: эмоциональность, эмоциональная устойчивость, образовательная эффективность.

The issue of interaction between the individual and the society has become one of the most urgent problems of the 21st century, and the solution of the problem has raised the science of psychology to a higher level. Especially at a time when the issue of education has risen to the level of state policy, the development of technology, increasing demands and responsibilities on the individual is causing an increase in the psychological approach to education and the individual. As a separate branch of general psychology, the science of child psychology aims to solve the problems of children's development based on its research field. The occurrence of psychoneurological, psychopathological diseases, manias (phone mania, computer mania) among children serve to justify our above opinion. It explains that the solution of these problems is one of the urgent issues of effective use of tools such as psychodiagnostics and correction. In turn, within the scope of child psychology and psychodiagnostics, the practical importance of psychocorrection of the emotional sphere of children of primary school age by means of play therapy becomes important. A question arises here. What is the content of play therapy? What is the need for psychotherapeutic activities with children? To what extent is it appropriate to rely on play therapy in the emotional sphere? We will try to answer these questions in the framework of our comprehensive article.

The game was first used in therapy in 1909 by Z. Freud. This corresponds to the clinical situation of Hans Jr. Treatment consisted of observing the child's father how to respond to his

son's behavior. This was the first reported case of a child's difficulties and problems having emotional causes. Until that time, experts believed that delinquency in children was caused only as a result of deficiencies in education and training. This, in turn, prevented a new approach to the child. The experimental works and approaches put forward by Z. Freud have damaged the accuracy of this idea. Since then, the game has been studied in a two-sided interpretation. The first is activity, and the second is in terms of therapeutic properties. Ultimately, play therapy emerged as a result of attempts to apply a psychoanalytic approach to working with children. After Z. Freud, Termina Hag-Helmuth emphasized that play is the most decisive moment in the child's psychoanalysis. He first drew attention to the difficulty of applying the methods used in adult therapy to children (Hugh-Hellmuth 1921). Psychoanalysts have found that children cannot describe their anxiety in words. In 1919, Melanie Klein (Klein M. 1955) began to use the game technique as a means of analysis when working with children under 6 years of age. According to him, children's games are based on malicious intent and free communication, just like the behavior of adults. Thus, play therapy made it possible to penetrate directly into the "subconscious" of children. (The term "play therapy" was introduced by M.K. Jain). Features of play therapy are characterized by compatibility with the child's psychological development processes. Also, the main type of activity of the child during the preschool age is play. In addition, A. Freud found that play is an important factor in establishing an emotional connection with a child. Both M. Klein and A. Frand believed that the game is a tool that makes the child free to express himself. The second main direction in the development of play therapy is explained by the emergence of the work of David Levy (Levy D. 1938) in the 1930s. This developed the idea of outreach therapy. In the process of implementing a past negative experience that causes a reaction of anxiety or fear, the child takes control of the game and changes from the passive role of the victim to an active person. Watching the game, the therapist displays verbal and non-verbal cues for the child. N.M. According to Aksarina, play does not arise by itself, there must be at least three conditions for it (for preschool children)

A) composition of impressions;

B) availability of toys and educational tools of various forms;

S) children's frequent interaction and communication with adults, in which the way adults directly influence the child is of decisive importance.

At the time, N.K. Krupskaya and A.S. Makarenko "the game not only educates the will, chaos, presence and initiative, but also creates a team, a sense of camaraderie, closeness and working for the interests of the team in one's actions. educates", they said. Pre-school children and their psycho-pedagogical characteristics are considered at the heart of the above thoughts. So, in the psychodiagnosis of children, the characteristics of individuality and age periods serve as an important factor.

The content of the game and its play in children of primary school age expands, and its factors increase. The content of the activity changes. If we look at the second aspect, the role of labor in children's activities will rise to an incomparable level. We know that if labor training is not properly trained, a selfish person who lives for his own benefit will be born. In this regard, game activity has a corrective nature and plays the role of a normative tool in education.

The Canadian scientist doctor G. Sel'e (1936-1976) added to the theories of U. Cannon with his 40 years of scientific research and said that stress is one of the main concepts in

psychology and medicine. G. Sel'e stress is not always harmful, sometimes it can help and benefit the human body. In some cases, when under stress, a person can become active in order to satisfy his need to fight for survival and use his energy in reserve that he did not know about. It is this feature that makes it possible to carry out a number of corrections in children, especially in children of small school age. In this sense, he studied the problem of adaptability of a living organism to unfavorable external conditions. According to G. Selni, these reasons cause significant and insignificant stress. These situations are related to each other. There are 3 stages.

In the stage of anxiety, the spleen shrinks, the fat layer disappears, acute inflammation occurs in the stomach, and there is a decrease in the number of lesions on the top of the kidney. At the same time, there is a decrease in skin lesions, tearing, and salivation. If the effect is strong, anxiety begins at this stage.

The nature and origin of the above medical symptoms make it necessary to correct them. Since play therapy is an activity that complements children's psychological capabilities and characteristics, turning educational activities into the main type of activity in children during this period leads to the occurrence of emotional disorders. This situation can be explained by the following factors.

Entering school is the beginning of a new responsible stage for the development of a child's personality. The content of the child's activity will also undergo a radical change. Therefore, the unity of school and family requirements for children of junior school age is important. From the beginning of school education, the child begins to be under a double educational influence. The first is the family, the second is the school. Therefore, it is extremely important that these educational influences are in the same direction. In most cases, the parent's approach to the child does not match the teacher's style. This, in turn, leads to changes in the child's psyche and emotional sphere. If this process is the opposite, it leads to a complete violation of the student's behavior or the formation of two different forms of behavior. In a brother-in-law, the characteristics of introversion, stubbornness and capriciousness become apparent. This, in turn, affects the child's learning process. D. B. Elkonin, V. V. Davydov and my students, on the one hand, and N. A. Menchinskaya, Ye. N.

Kabanova-Müller and my followers, on the other hand, are used in the educational process far from the predominance of practical and theoretical types of generalization years of scientific debate. In our opinion, educational materials are unique depending on the characteristics, any method of generalization has a high effect point, but to admit that one or the other is 1 absolute is both methodological and it would have been a practical-methodical error. It should be said that as the scope of knowledge of primary school students expands, the thinking of the subjects of education begins to move from firm judgments to approximate judgments, because they have different aspects of things and phenomena, characteristics, laws and properties. rise to the stage of realizing that reality does not originate from one action, one reason, but is created as a result of many causes, effects, instigators. The interests of children of this period are also unique. According to psychologists, first of all, interests are formed in relation to certain facts, single events isolated from other things. (Grades 1-2). The final conclusion is that a number of structural structures of a person, such as the formation of a child's personality, adaptability to the environment, improvement of the protection function, are laid through the game. Therefore, the organization of psychocorrective activities through the game is considered the optimal method of forming correctional skills in the student.

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